

*Proto-Indo-European *peh₂- the source of Pan, had the older meaning “fat, thick”, and Ancient Greek Hermes is from Thracian *Sermas/*Sermes, *Sarmas/*Sarmes= “fattener”, from PIE *k^hermo-, *k^hormō -= “fat, thick; glutton”, source also of French gourmand which was of unknown origin until now; and source of Romanian grumaz and Albanian gurmaz; of Ukrainian soromoxa= “wolverine”; and with Uralic cognates as well; and PIE *k^hermo-, *k^hormō I posit are in turn from PIE *k^her-, “fat, thick; to fatten, to thicken, to grow, to nourish”; PIE *ser, “to bind; to put together” and PIE *ser “to guard, to protect” are old Pre-PIE variants of this *k^her-, but, as Beekes concluded, *ser is not the source of Hermes and herma*

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Sometime in 2022 or early 2023, I had realized that the older meaning (perhaps the oldest meaning) of PIE *peh₂- was “fat, thick”, which led to “to fatten; to nourish; to feed”, and from there “to take care of; to protect; to graze; to ward; to shepherd”, as I will demonstrate in this paper,(it seems that no one besides me has proposed this yet).

It may not have been until February 3rd 2024 that I realized (or once again realized) that Ancient Greek πᾶς “all, every, each; whole” (Aeolic form παῖς; Cretan, Thessalian and Arcadocypriot form πάνσα) and its combining/prefix forms παν-, παμ-, παγ- (and derivative forms such as παντοῖος) derive from “nourished, protected>safe>whole” (I think this has been posited before by certain previous linguists, since I have seen πᾶς “all, every, each; whole” and its variants and derivatives stated as deriving from PIE *peh₂-; in an upcoming edition, I will find such references for that).

For such a semantic shift, I compare examples such as PIE *h₂el- “to grow, nourish”, which I posit is the root of Proto-Germanic *allaz=“all, whole, entire”, even though I have seen sources deriving Proto-Germanic *allaz=“all, whole, entire” from an identical-sounding root that had different meanings: PIE *h₂el- “beyond; other”; but that derivation has not become consensus. PIE *h₂el- “beyond, other” in my estimation probably comes from “to grow far out” leading to “to extend far out” which led to “beyond”; and “beyond, far out” could easily have led to “stranger” and to “other”. See also PIE *h₂el- “to wander, roam” which is probably from “(travelling) far out, extending far out”.

I also compare Old Armenian ողջ (oġ) which has the meanings “alive, living, sound, safe; complete, entire, whole, integral” and which linguistic works derive from either PIE *h₂el- (see above) or from PIE *solh₂- “whole”.

And it may not have been until February 3rd 2024 that I realized (or once again realized) that Ancient Greek παιάν (“a chant or song, especially a thanksgiving or victory hymn, to Apollo under the name Παῖάν), Παιάν (a name of Apollo, especially of Apollo as a healing-god); Παιών (the physician of the gods); παιών (a physician); παιωνία / παιονία (=the peony flowering plant whose root was highly prized as healing many ills) ; Παιώνιος (=an adjective meaning “medicinal, healing”); Παιονία (the

land of the Paiones/Paionians); and Παιονίς derive from “to nourish, to protect” leading to “to heal, to make whole, to make healthy; medicinal, healing”. I have seen no linguist positing this before.

The name of the Ancient Greek god Πᾶν meant “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” in the older days, later likely understood more as “Protector, Guardian, Shepherd”. In my next edition I will detail some variant forms of Πᾶν. The PIE form of Pan and its Sanskrit cognate Pūṣán was reconstructed as *Péh₂-usōn by Hermann Collitz in 1924. See “Wodan, Hermes und Pushan,” *Festschrift tillägnad Hugo Pipping på Hans sextioårsdag den 5 November 1924*; 1924, pp 574–587.

So in summary, I posit that PIE *peh₂, “to protect, to ward; to shepherd; to feed, to nourish, to graze” actually derives from “to fatten” in turn from “fat, thick, dense”. This is shown by two PIE roots which I posit derive from *peh₂: PIE *peh₂ǵ (source of words referring to things that are firm, fastened, dense, thick) and PIE *peh₂k̑- (another source of words referring to things that are firm, fastened, dense, thick).

Part 2: Hermes, from Thracian or Pelasgian; and the meanings of Latin Faunus/Fauna and Illyrian Daunus and more

After a number of years of study, my conclusion is that Hermes (Ἑρμῆς, Ἑρμᾶς, Ἑρμάων, Ἑρμῶν, Ἑρμείας, Ἑρμείης) had the meaning “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” and also “Binder; Throttler/Strangler” (“Binder” referring to a magician, whose spells bind; and “Throttler, Strangler” referring to how wolves strangle/throttle their prey, but also referring to a god that can throttle wolves: in this case, it was surely a case of fighting fire with fire: like having power over like: a god who was often thought of as a wolf keeping wolves at bay and throttling wolves) and derives from a Thracian or Pelasgian (if Pelasgian sibilized/satemized initial *k̑- into S, as did Thracian¹) theonym *Sermes/*Sermas/*Sarmas/*Sarmes, meaning “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” and also “Binder; Throttler/Strangler”, and deriving from PIE *kerm-, *korm-, from PIE or Pre-PIE *ker-, “fat, thick; to fatten, to thicken, to grow, to nourish”, a root which was hitherto thought to have less meanings in PIE: “to grow, to make grow; to nourish”.

This PIE or Pre-PIE *ker-, “fat, thick; to fatten, to thicken, to grow, to nourish”, I posit is cognate to and the source of PIE *ker-, “to plait, to weave; rope, string”; and I posit this because of the following: we find similar parallels in the Uralic, Proto-Eskimo, and Turkic languages; see: Proto-Uralic *kuḍa- “morning, dawn” and Proto-Uralic *kuḍa- ‘weave’ (no Ugric or Samoyed cognates); words for “morning, dawn” sometimes derive from “to grow”, see for example Ancient Greek ὄρθρος meaning “the time immediately before or around sunrise, early morning, dawn”, and deriving from PIE *h₃erdh “to increase, grow; upright, high”. So I posit that Proto-Uralic *kuḍa- “morning, dawn” may derive from the earlier meanings “to grow” in turn from “to thicken; firm”², in turn from “thick, firm, hard” or “thick, firm, fat”: probably “thick, firm, fat” is the better choice, since “fat” is closer to

1 It’s also possible that Hermes and herma are from a language where initial *k̑- became initial H, or from a language where initial *k̑- became G, then became H: neither of these scenarios would correspond to what is known of Thracian, but they may correspond to Pelasgian, of which very little is known; or some other ancient language once spoken in the region.

2 As I posited in one of Geoffrey Caveney’s Uralic/Proto-Eskimo sessions on Academia.edu back in December of 2022; besides I and Geoffrey Caveney, the session was attended by numerous linguists of today, including Mikhail Zhivlov, Arnaud Fournet, Juho Pystynen, and numerous others, all of whom witnessed and read my comments in December 2022.

“growing”: and yet the penis grows when it thickens/fattens and gets harder, so “hard” fits as well³. Since I connect Northern Sami *guormes* (“thick flour, rough skin”) to PIE **ker-*, I do not think that these Uralic **kuḍa-* forms derive from **ker-*, instead I think the Uralic **kuḍa-* forms are semantically parallel to the two PIE **ker-* roots, but not cognate.

As Geoffrey Caveney first posited in 2022⁴, the Uralic **kuḍa-* forms described above may be cognate to the following Proto-Eskimo and Aleut words: Proto-Eskimo **qilay-* ‘sky’, Aleut *qila-x̄* ‘morning, dawn’; Proto-Eskimo **qilay-* “knit, weave” (no Aleut cognate). Even if not cognate to the Uralic words, the Proto-Eskimo and Aleut words very likely come from the kind of root-meanings that I described above. See also how Proto-Turkic **ör-* meant “to rise” and “to plait”⁵.

The caduceus of Hermes shows---below the two bird wings---a staff around which two serpents coil/entwine: PIE **ker-* “to plait, to weave; rope, string” relates to the coils on the caduceus staff and to weaving spells, binding spells (Hermes was associated a lot with magic/spell-casting: this is seen for example when Ancient Greeks identified Thoth with Hermes, and Ancient Egyptians identified Hermes with Thoth): my etymology encompasses magic because most magic was understood/conceived of as a binding, as in the term “spellbinding”: and “binding” is akin to coils, bands, straps, which are some of the attested meanings of *herma* (ἔρμα) and binding is again from “to twist a cord/string around something so that you make it firm<to make firm<firm, thick”. See for example Armenian “pind” meaning: “firm, dense, tight, strong, fastened” and “pind” is cognate to English “bind”.

So the Ancient Greek word *herma* (ἔρμα) included the meanings “strap, band; noose; coil”: PIE **ker-* “to plait, to weave; rope, string” as I posited above derives from the older meanings “to make firm, firm, thick, dense” (many words for “rope, string, band” derive from “to tighten, to make firm” and many words for a skein of thread derive from “thick, fat” and the threads on a bobbin, when there are many threads on a bobbin, make a fat lump/fat bulk on the bobbin) and PIE **ker-* “to grow, nourish” as I posited above also derives from Pre-PIE “fat, thick, dense”, leading also to a swelling, such as a hill, and “hill” is one of the meanings of Ancient Greek *herma* (ἔρμα) : though in “hill” meanings derived from this root, the hill was also thought of as a dense fat firm lump, not just the idea of swollen/fat.

My etymology also encompasses the staff of the caduceus, which is a pole: and PIE **peh₂ǵ* is considered to be the source of Latin *palus* which means “stake, pole”, and the root of Hermes, Pre-PIE **ker-* (as described above), is very semantically similar to **peh₂ǵ* and **peh₂* (and in Part 1 of this paper I posit that **peh₂ǵ* derives from **peh₂*).

So now one can see why I posit that Hermes (and Pan, for that matter; and Faunus and Fauna in Latin) meant “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” and “Binder”; but one may ask, but what about “Throttler/Strangler”? The meanings “throttler, strangler” easily come from “to make firm, to make tight”. I will detail that more later in Part 3 of this paper, where I will detail my conclusion that Latin

3 Excuse me for this; I’m a heterosexual man, but there was no way to avoid discussing this in this paper; and the herm pillar of Hermes is considered to have had phallic connotations, and surely it did. Besides, I’m thinking of my own penis when I discuss this.

4 See Caveney, Geoffrey (2022), *Uralic-Eskimo intervocalic consonant correspondences and first vowel correspondences (revised and expanded)*.

5 I first mentioned this Proto-Turkic **ör-* meaning “to rise” and “to plait” example in connection with the preceding examples in the summer of 2023 in one of Peter S. Piispanen’s sessions on Yukaghir and Chukchi, as a follow-up to what I had posted in that Geoffrey Caveney session in December of 2022.

Faunus and Fauna and Illyrian Daunus/Dauna also had this double set of meanings: “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” and also “Binder; Throttler/Strangler”.

But before I detail the evidence outside of Greek, I will first continue to detail the evidence within Ancient Greek: herma (ἕρμα) in Ancient Greek was of undetermined etymology before this paper. Some of the meanings of the word were: “hill; heap of stones; reef, rock”: these all derive (as I will demonstrate) from “thick, dense, massive” akin to “fat”; and had a number of meanings referring to a stable/stabilizing, strong, dense entity: “a prop, a support, foundation, stay (of a ship), ballast”--- these again are all from “thick, dense, firm, weighty, strong”. And the word also referred to a “band, a noose, coils”, all of which make firm: so these derive from “to make firm”, from “firm”. From “coil” developed the meaning “ear-ring”, which is also attested. The meanings “defense, cause” also attested for this word come from “something firm, a firm foundation” which can be a firm defense and a firm cause on which to base one’s actions.

Considering all the attested meanings, this word ἕρμα (herma) does not fit well the PIE *ser- “to string together, to bind, to put together”, and that is why the etymology/the root remained a matter of dispute and debate. Robert S. P. Beekes, one of the world’s main authorities on Ancient Greek, concluded that Hermes and herma are not from PIE *ser. Beekes preferred to think that Hermes is from a Non-IE Pre-Greek language; I will check to see whether he thought the same about herma (ἕρμα), but even if he did not (and probably he did), some other scholars of Ancient Greek did come to the conclusion that herma (ἕρμα) is of Non-IE Pre-Greek origin. I agree that herma (ἕρμα) and Hermes are not from *ser, but I derive them from an IE language, either from Thracian (which could have been a Pre-Greek language in some regions of Greece) or Pelasgian (which very likely was an Indo-European language, and was a Pre-Greek language).

Let us consider also this quote, not from Beekes but from another source:

“ ἕρμα

etymology disputed:

- Perhaps related to εἶρω (eíro, “I string together”)+μα (-ma), from PIE *ser-, “to string together, to bind, to put together”.
- Alternatively, cognate with Sanskrit वरुष्मन् (varuṣman, “protrusion, summit, peak, top, vertex”), from [Proto-Indo-European](#) *wérsman (“protrusion, bump, hill, summit, peak, top”) and, via the root *wers- (“to rise, protrude; peak”), Lithuanian viršus (“top”), Old Church Slavonic връхъ (vrǫxŭ, “top, peak”), and probably Proto-Germanic *wartō (“wart”). However, the Mycenaean Greek cognate e-ma-ta > *hémata=“straps”, (plural) lacks the expected (expected if *wers- was actually the root) initial */w/, as does Mycenaean Greek e-ma-ha < *hémaha=“Hermes”.
- A conflation of these two.”

Compare Ancient Greek πάγος meaning “mountain, rocky hill; frost (that which has congealed into something thicker than water); the scum on the surface of milk”, and πάγος is already known to be from PIE *peh₂ǵ mentioned in Part 1, which I posit is derived from PIE *peh₂ “fat, thick”, already by consensus determined to be the source of the theonym Pan, and Pan was a version of the same god that became Hermes (see the literature on that subject of Pan and Hermes).

As Beekes et al. have concluded, the word ἕρμα (herma) and the theonym Hermes in fact do not derive from PIE *ser-, as indicated phonetically and semantically by Ancient Greek εἶρω (eiro) which is from PIE *ser, “to bind together, to put together” and which is far in form and meaning from Hermes and herma: Ancient Greek εἶρω (eiro) meant “to tie, join, fasten, string together; to insert”. The meanings and form of εἶρω (eiro) are primarily why Beekes doesn’t think Hermes and herma are from *ser. There is also Ancient Greek ὄρμος (hórmos) meaning “a cord, a chain, especially a necklace, a collar; anything strung like a necklace, a wreath, a chaplet; a kind of dance performed in a ring“. This ὄρμος (hórmos) word is probably from *ser: the form is close to Hermes and herma, but the meanings are again far from a number of the meanings that herma has, especially: “hill, rock, reef, pillar, pile of stones”.

We see that there is PIE *k^{er}, “to grow, to make grow; to nourish”; we see that there is PIE *k^{er}, “to weave, to plait; rope, string”; we see that there is PIE *k^{er}s, “to run”; I conclude (see the following paragraph for the reason why) that the root-meaning linking all three is “force, strength, power”, which led to “thick, strong, firm, fat” for the first two mentioned, and led to “to run>to flow” for the third root mentioned.

And I see that there is PIE *ser, “to guard, to protect”; there is PIE *ser, “to bind together, string together, put together”; there is PIE *ser, “to flow” (in very many languages, Indo-European and Non-Indo-European, “to run” leads to “to flow” and vice versa)---so I conclude that the root-meaning linking all three is “force, strength, power”, which led to “thick, strong, firm, fat” for the first two mentioned, and led to “to run>to flow” for the third root mentioned; and I conclude that *ser was an old pre-PIE variant of the root from which Hermes and herma derive, but *ser is most likely not the root of Hermes and herma, for the reasons Beekes et al. have described and for the reasons described in this paper. The Ancient Greek words that derive from *ser “to guard, to protect” have the forms: ῥύομαι (rhúomai), εἰρύομαι (eirúomai), which linguistically speaking (to the linguist’s trained eye) are far from Hermes and herma.

Nor are Hermes and herma from PIE *wers-, a root mentioned in that quote earlier. Nor are Hermes and herma from PIE *k^wer, “to do, to make, to build”. Nor is Hermes from the root of Ancient Greek ὀρμή meaning “rapid motion forwards, onrush, onset, assault”, which is cognate with Ancient Greek ὀρμάω meaning “to set in motion, urge on, cheer on”, which is from PIE *h₃er- “to move, to stir (to stir as in to arouse from a state of stillness; not “to stir” as in stirring a cup of tea); to rise, to spring, to leap; to quarrel, to fight”. From PIE *h₃er- also derives (if no one else has posited this before) Ancient Greek ἐρμή, a word attested only in a Hesychius gloss, where he defines it as: ἔξοδος=“going out, exiting”, no doubt with a sense of force and speed as seen with the word ὀρμή meaning “rapid motion forwards”.

From PIE *k^{er} came the PIE forms *k^{erm}-, *k^{orm}- which had the meanings “thick, dense, massive, fat, strong, firm; fattening, nourishing, binding etc.”, and from “fat” developed the meanings “glutton, gluttonous”, as we shall see; and precisely such a shift in meaning is encountered in Chuvash kanap (kapar) deriving from Proto-Turkic *kēp- meaning “to swell, swollen (of belly); to become

pregnant; to be arrogant, inflated” (see for example Turkish *gebe*=“pregnant”; Azerbaijani *qəbiz*=“constipation”).

In Ukrainian, we find a dialectal (Čerkassian dialect) word *soromáxa* meaning “wolverine”, an animal synonymous with gluttony in human cultures: in fact *Gulo*, the scientific name for the genus to which the wolverine belongs, means “glutton” in Latin, and by Medieval Latin also meant “wolverine”; the source of *gulo* is Latin *gula* meaning “gullet”. For Ukrainian *soromáxa* it is possible to think about the Slavic proto-form **sormaxa* (Vasmer 3,504-505; Machek 1968, 517).

From here, I will quote Vaclav Blazek’s 2013 paper on the etymology of Hermes, even though he did not realize that Hermes meant “Fattener, Feeder, Nourisher; Binder etc.” and that these wolverine and weasel and wolf words (and some other animals as we shall see) derive from “glutton”:

“With respect to Ukrainian dialect variant (Čerkassian) *soromáxa*, it is possible to think about the Slavic proto-form **sormaxa* (Vasmer 3,504-505; Machek 1968, 517). Separating the expressive suffix **-axъ/*-axa* or the nominalizing suffix **-akъ* (cf. Sławski 1974, 71-72; 89-90), the root proper is **sorm-* . . . Trubačev (apud Vasmer) compared this Slavic root **sorm-* with Lithuanian *šarmu*, *šermu* "ermine" and German Hermelin "ermine", Old High German *harmilī(n)*, *harmil*, *harmo*; Old Saxon *harmo*, Old English *hearma* "weasel"; Rhaeto-Romance *carmun* "weasel / *Mustela minuta*", and Rhaeto-Romance *carnung*, *carmun* "ermine / *Mustela erminea*", perhaps from Venetic or Gaulish substrata (HwR 155) <**kormōn/*kermōn*, and further perhaps to **kormo-* attested in Lithuanian *šarmas* & *šarmà* "hoarfrost" (Kluge 1999, 371; Pokorny 1959, 573-74)”⁶

But then Blazek goes on to say that since those words derive from a root with initial **k̑-*, they cannot be cognate with Greek Hermes: but Blazek was wrong about that: *because they can be cognate with Hermes and herma if Hermes and herma were loans from Thracian or from another language that sibilized/satemized the initial *k̑ sound.*

Whether an initial **k̑* sound would exclude Hittite *sarmiya* (*sarmiya* referred to an unidentified kind of wild predatory animal) and Vedic *Sarāmā* (a deity often equated with Hermes by modern scholars, and a deity that was conceived of as a female dog of the gods) I’m not sure; but likely loanwords are involved in the Hittite and Vedic examples: or the Vedic *Sarāmā* is from PIE **ser*, “to flow, to run” as many scholars believe, from many references to such a speedy attribute in the Indian traditions about *Sarāmā*. Hittite *sarmiya* and Vedic *Sarāmā* may be from the old **ser* variants of PIE **ker*, which includes an ancient **ser* that meant “to protect, to guard<to nourish<to fatten” (so Hittite *sarmiya* can be from “glutton<fat”), as well as **ser*, “to flow, to run” (from “force, strength, power” in this case akin to “thick, fat”) and **ser* “to bind” (from “to make firm, firm”).

The reader should be aware that weasels, like wolverines, were very much thought of as voracious gluttons, and surely some words for weasel are confirmed to derive from voracious and/or glutton. And note how we find Lithuanian *šarmas* and *šarmà* "hoarfrost", which Blazek seems to have correctly realized are cognate to the words referring to various animals (judging from his paper though,

⁶ Blazek, Vaclav. *Hermes*. In: Sources of Mythology. Ancient and Contemporary Myths. Proceedings of the Seventh Annual International Conference on Comparative Mythology (Tübingen; 15 -17 May 2013), ed. by Klaus Antoni & David Weiss. Wien: Lit-Verlag 2014, 231-245. (totally 376 pp.)

Blazek thought the connection was “to flow, to run”, referring to fast animals and to dripping hoarfrost, which is congealed water). See how one of the meanings of Ancient Greek πᾶγος was “frost”.

Another quote from Blazek’s paper:

“It is possible to demonstrate still deeper roots of the Indo-European zoonym reconstructible in all qualitative apophonic grades: *sem-/som-/sɨm-, if the Nostratic level is taken in account: Uralic *śurme "wild animal" (UEW 490-91) > Saami Kld. *tśirm*; Ko. Not. *tśerma*, "wolf; devil" | Mari KB *sərmə*, U *šurmaŋye*, *šurmaŋše*, B *šurmaŋše* "lynx" | Khanty DN *türəm*, Ni. *Śurəm* "ermine, (snow-)weasel, marten" || Samoyedic *sarma (Janhunen 1977, 136; Helimski 1997, 335) > Nenets O *sārmik* "predator, wolf; animal", *pīn-sārma* "owl" (pi=night); Enets *same* "wolf"; Selkup Ta. *suurem*, Ke. *súuram*, *súurm*, N *húurup*, Tur. *sūríp* "wild animal"; Tur. *t̪ımpitil sūríp* "bird"; Karagassian *sarma* "hazel grouse / Tetrao bonasia" “

In 2020, before I read Blazek’s paper, I had noted down in my notebook the Northern Sami word *guormes* meaning “thick flour, rough skin”.

I further posit as cognates French *gourmand* and Middle French and Old French *gourmant* (“glutton” and “gluttonous”): both of these French words are previously un-etymologized, of unknown origin and unknown root. And I further posit as cognates Romanian *grumaz* “neck; adam’s apple; nape; small hill”: for “small hill” recall the hill meanings seen above for Ancient Greek *herma* and πᾶγος (*pagos*) and for “neck” recall Latin *gula* meaning “gullet” which led to *Gulo*, a Medieval Latin word for the wolverine as a gluttonous animal. Albanian *gurmaz* (“esophagus”) is another cognate. The Romanian word is already considered a Pre-Roman word cognate with the Albanian word, and they are previously un-etymologized.

My etymology of *Hermes* encompasses most of his main attributes: protector of flocks, god of shepherds; god of healing and medicine (see how I conclude that *Pan* and *Paian*, god of healing, are cognates) since the *caduceus* has that association even though *Apollo*, *Paian* and *Asclepius* handled most of the healing and medicine domains in Classical Ancient Greece; and my theory encompasses *Hermes* as god of borders: because I derive *herma*, which referred to the *herm* pillar stone and to a pile of stones, from a root that meant “firm, thick, fat”: this fits all the meanings attested for *herma* in Ancient Greek; and see how PIE **peh*₂ǵ is the source of words that fit exactly what the *herma* pillar was, and I derive PIE **peh*₂ǵ from Pre-PIE **peh*₂, "fat, thick; to fatten, to nourish, to make firm, to make fat, to make strong, to make whole, to make healthy", while in PIE **peh*₂ meant "to nourish, to feed, to take care of".

Even the thievery and trickster attributes fit my theory well because the root that I posit for *Hermes* was also the root for many words that applied to jackals (recall the coyote trickster of many Amerindians) and weasels and martens and ferrets and the wolf (the wolf is associated with the trickster *Loki*): weasels, martens and ferrets are thieves, weasels steal chickens and chicken eggs, jackals do as well, wolves are thieves of chickens and larger livestock and of children sometimes (jackals too).

The root that I posit is the source of words for these animals because the root in those cases developed the meaning "glutton", derived from the meaning “fat”, as we see in the Turkic examples.

My theory also encompasses the speed of Hermes, since the oldest meaning of the root was “force, strength, power”, which led on the one hand to “fat, thick, firm” and on the other hand to “to run”, and from there “to flow”.

The speed of Hermes is such a part of Hermes in mythology/ancient religion because Hermes was a god of borders, and as a god of borders he was also a god of “in-between”, and as a god of “in-between”, he became (if he was not already) the messenger god, the one who goes between gods and men and between gods and titans (which is why Hermes visited Prometheus on behalf of Zeus) and so on: and as a messenger, he would have to be fast like human messengers/couriers who often had to deliver their message running the whole time. And speed is also involved with the speed of many of those animal predators, the words for which---those mentioned earlier as well as some unattested ones---are cognates to Hermes. The rapidity of the planet Mercury’s passage through the sky is the main reason why the planet Mercury was associated with Hermes.

But I do not argue that there developed necessarily a folk-association with PIE **ǵ*kers, “to run” and/or with PIE **ser*, “to flow” and/or with PIE **h*₃*er*- “to move with force, to leap, to spring (and more meanings)”, though those roots could have re-enforced the speed aspect of Hermes; but more likely the speed aspect of Hermes comes down from the time when “to run, to flow” was still an active part of the polysemy of the root-word **ǵ*ker.

In the next update, of course I will have even more evidence, and I will detail the wolf associations that Hermes can be determined to have had (for now, the reader may read Blazek’s paper on Hermes for more details about that).

It’s very likely that Dacian Sarmi-/Sarme- (found in the Dacian toponym Sarmizegethousa, the main fortress of the Dacians---with a number of variants---and in Sarmetegte, another Dacian toponym) meant “fortress” and derives from “thick, strong, firm”.

Part 3: Mercurius and merx and Faunus, Fauna in Latin, and Etruscan Turms and Selvans

I conclude that *Mercurius* meant (before this knowledge was lost to the Romans/Latins and others) “Fattener, Nourisher, Feeder” and likely also “Binder, Throtter, Strangler” (see Part 2 for that).

Latin *merx* had the meanings “goods, wares, commodities, merchandise”, and could include food: “*merx esculenta*” refers to food in Ovid’s *Metamorphoses*, 13.165. I conclude that *merx* derives from the earlier meaning “livestock”, in turn from the earlier meaning “Nourished, Fed”, e.g., animals that were raised by people, tended, led to graze, fed by people, etc.

For the semantic shift “livestock” to “goods, merchandise”, compare the very similar shift seen with Latin *pecunia* (=money, wealth) deriving from Latin *pecu*, which meant “cattle; domestic animals”.

PIE **merǵ*- / **marǵ*- “edge, boundary, border” I conclude derives from earlier **merǵ*- / **marǵ*- referring to boundary stones (herms): be it a pillar herm, or a herm as a pile of stones. In turn, I posit

that these boundary stone/herm meanings derive from “thick, dense, fat”; whether in turn these meanings come from other, earlier meanings: I haven’t yet found any indications of that.

For marg- having stony meanings, see Latin *marga*, which meant “marl” (and “marl” derives from Latin *marga*), which means “a mixed earthy substance, which is calcareous, clayey, sandy”; the Latin *marga* has been compared with Welsh *marian* meaning “rocks, pebbles, grit; rocky debris; rock-strewn land”, from Proto-Brythonic **mary-*.

Two recent theories^{7 8} from two other linguists I reject because they would make Mercurius have a meaning that doesn’t fit with Hermes, Faunus, and Pan; and I see enough evidence to conclude that Mercurius actually had the same semantics as Hermes, Faunus, and Pan originally did, and the same kind of semantic origin, at least mostly the same.

Here are their theories:

“Nikolaev reconstructs Proto-Indo-European **merk-*-, relating *merx* to Ancient Greek [μάρπτω](#) (*márptō*, “to take hold”) and Tocharian A [märk-](#) (“to take away”).” My comment: if this were to be true, and if Mercurius has the same origin as *merx*, then this would relate Mercurius to thievery as well as to trade/commerce/goods: and the theonym would exclude all other aspects of Mercury/Mercurius.

“Matasović instead derives *merx* from a root **merǵ-* (“to divide”), whence also Latin *margo* (“border”), Proto-Celtic **mrogis*, Proto-Germanic **markō*, and Persian *marz*; the verbal sense of which survives in Hittite [𒍪𒀭𒍪](#) [𒍪𒀭𒍪](#) [𒍪𒀭𒍪](#) (*mar-ak-zi* /*marktsi*/, “to cut up, separate, divide, distribute”). The connection to Hittite was in fact already suggested by Puhvel (2004). Matasović posits that this root **merǵ-* may itself be an extension of [*mer-](#) (“to divide, apportion, allot”).”

So we now have at least three good theories, and in the future we can try to determine which one is historically true. For my theory, I conclude that the PIE root **(s)mer*, **mer*, “to divide, apportion, allot” is not the source of Latin *merx* nor of Mercurius, and is unrelated to *merx* and Mercurius. The Hittite word *marktsi*, “to cut up, separate, divide, distribute” probably derives from **(s)mer*, **mer* and is unrelated to *merx* and Mercurius.

I conclude that Faunus and Fauna in Latin---a god and goddess of nature, animals, spring and fertility---derive from a PIE root **d^heh₂u-/*d^heu-* that meant “fat, thick, firm; to fatten, to nourish”, cognate to another PIE root **d^heh₂u-/*d^heu-/*d^hau* that meant “to bind; to make firm; to fasten; to press together, to crush, to strangle” and deriving from a Pre-PIE **d^heh₂u-/*d^heu-* that meant “force, strength; power”, a root which is also the source of PIE **d^heu-* “to run>to flow” and the source of PIE **d^heh₁-* “to do, to put, to place” (see my recent January 2024 paper on PIE **d^heh₁-* for an explanation of this) and the source of PIE **d^heh₁-* “to suck”: which is either from: “to place at the nipple” as De Vaan posited recently; or from “to press the lips together”; or, probably most likely from “to breastfeed”, in turn from “to nourish<to fatten<fat, thick”.

7 See Nikolaev, Alexander (2021), “Etyma Graeca II”, in *Indo-European Linguistics and Classical Philology*, issue 25, Institute for Linguistic Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences, pages 953–976.

8 See Matasović, Ranko (June 30, 2022), “Four Latin Etymologies: *volgus*, *laedo*, *paedor*, *merx*”, in *Latina et Graeca*, volume 2, issue 41, pages 7–16

I conclude that Etruscan Turms (the name of an Etruscan deity equivalent to Hermes and Mercury) is cognate with PIE *térμη “boundary, end”, and PIE *térμη may come from a *ter variant of PIE *ser and PIE *ker, as described in part 2.

Part 4: Saturos (Satyr) is very likely from PIE *seh₂, “to satiate, satisfy”

I have published two other etymologies of Ancient Greek σατυρος (“a satyr; a lewd person”), one of them⁹ focusing on the sexual and virile aspect (Sa + Turos, with the hypothetical Thracian or dialectal Greek Sa corresponding to the known and attested Ancient Greek Za- meaning “very”; I took this Thracian Sa- from the Thracian anthroponym Satokos/Sadokos, since tokos, dokos, takos is a discrete Thracian anthroponym element which occurs in a number of Thracian names; while “Turos” might be from PIE *tewh₂- “to swell; powerful, strong”);

and another focusing on the wild aspect¹⁰, with σατυρος deriving via a Thracian dialect from a hypothetical PIE *k^wetwóres meaning “fire-holder” or “lightning-holder”, referring to wood and stone: from “wood” I posited the semantic shift “of the woods”, and from there meaning “wild” and from there saturos as “the wild one”.

And two unpublished etymologies from my notebook (first published here, but these are not my newest theory which I will describe after these two), one deriving σατυρος from the meanings “goader; to prick; pointed” if PIE *k^wetwóres meant “goader”, since in ancient Indo-European culture the four-armed swastika was associated with the Axis Mundi and the force that drives/goads the Axis Mundi. In this scenario, the satyr would be a chief goat leading the others, as Tituros in Ancient Greek was another word for satyr as well as a word for a bellwether ram that leads the flock; and in this scenario, saturos would again have a sexual focus (“to prick”) as well as a mystical-mythological association with the force or forces that germinate seeds (pricking them to sprout, pricking animals and human women to give birth) and the force that drives the axis mundi.

Regardless of the etymology of Saturos, I have come to the conclusion that Tituros most likely derives from a Tit- word meaning “pointed; to goad, to drive”, contrary to the theory that I published in December 2023 about Tituros, where I posited that the root of Tituros is Tur, “to swell, strong” which would be reduplicated (reduplication is rather common in Ancient Greek words) from PIE *tewh₂- “to swell; powerful, strong”. To this hypothetical Tit- meaning “to prick, to drive; pointed”, I link (via the semantic shift “to prick, to goad>to drive>axle/wheel/that which rotates as if driven”) the unetymologized native Romanian word țiteică meaning “a plank stuck horizontally into a firm pole of wood, arranged in such a way that the plank can rotate, serving as an activity similar to a game of carousel. 2. a plank placed across a tree-stump or something similar in shape and density to a tree-stump so that the board’s ends can be used as a see-saw by children when one does not have a real see-saw at hand” ; as well as the un-etymologized native Romanian word țitei which means “oil” as in

9 In my paper from December 2023 focusing on the etymologies of the Thracian names Spartacus, Rhoimetalkes, and Satacus/Sadocus.

10 In my January 2024 paper on the root-meanings of the PIE root of Avis and Ovis (bird and sheep).

petroleum oil, and which I derive from a hypothetical ἵτ= “to prick”, referring to how the oil gushes/flows out of the ground as if pricked/goaded/agitated to erupt out.

Returning to *saturos*, the third unpublished etymology from my notebooks is that *saturos* derives from a root with the form $*\acute{k}\acute{e}t$ and is cognate to Sanskrit *satru* meaning “enemy, foe, rival”, which is already posited to derive from a root $*\acute{k}\acute{e}t$ meaning “angry”¹¹, which in this scenario at least I derive from an earlier $*\acute{k}\acute{e}t$ meaning “goaded”, in turn from a $*\acute{k}\acute{e}t$ meaning ‘pointed, sharp’. But in this scenario, *saturos* would not mean “angry” nor “enemy, rival”, but instead meant “wild” from “goaded”, as well as possibly having the additional meanings described above where I discuss the meanings that *saturos* could have had if *saturos* derives from a $*k^{wetw}\acute{o}res$ that meant “goader” rather than “fire-holder” or “lightning-holder”.

Now I will discuss my theory that $\sigma\acute{\alpha}\tau\upsilon\rho\acute{o}\varsigma$ derives from PIE $*seh_2$, “to satiate, satisfy”: this would mean the Satyr was originally conceived as a Pan/Hermes figure/deity. This theory has the advantage over the two $*k^{wetw}\acute{o}res$ derived-theories in that it does not require invoking a new Thracian dialect, since we elsewhere we find *Ketri-* in Thracian *Ketriporis* very likely deriving from $*k^{wetw}\acute{o}res$ (but not necessarily from the meaning “four”); and in the Moesian *Kjolmen* inscription, the element *Katroso* very likely meant “stone”, deriving from $*k^{wetw}\acute{o}r-$ (either because $*k^{wetw}\acute{o}res$ had the earlier meanings “stone” and “wood” or in reference to a quadrilateral stone slab). However, there were dialects/variant idioms of Thracian and Daco-Thracian, which is why we find *kinouboila* in Dacian corresponding to a Thracian form *sinupyla*.

And this derivation from $*seh_2$, “to satiate, satisfy” has an advantage over a derivation from a $*\acute{k}\acute{e}t$ meaning ‘pointed, sharp’ because in Thracian and Dacian, we find instead a *Kot(t)-* meaning “pointed, sharp; to prick, to drive; axis, axle” (see my January 2024 paper on the etymologies of *Artemis* and *Artio*, *Kotys* and *Kottyto* et al.), and this *Kot(t)-* would be the Thracian version/variant of the root that gave rise to the Sanskrit word *satru* : but the root of *Kot(t)-* would not have a palatalized initial $*\acute{k}-$ sound, instead it would be a regular initial *k-* sound: so there may have been in Thracian both a root of this type with initial $*\acute{k}-$, and a variant root of this type with initial *k-*, unpalatalized.

In conclusion, it is very likely that the *Sat-* portion of *Saturos* (*Satyr*) derives from PIE $*seh_2$, “to satiate, satisfy”, and the rest of the word would show the same suffixes seen in the Ancient Greek word $\mu\acute{\alpha}\rho\tau\upsilon\rho\acute{o}\varsigma$, the Epic form of $\mu\acute{\alpha}\rho\tau\upsilon\rho$, the source of “martyr” (otherwise in Ancient Greek, outside of Epic, $\mu\acute{\alpha}\rho\tau\upsilon\rho\acute{o}\varsigma$ is the genitive form of $\mu\acute{\alpha}\rho\tau\upsilon\rho$). My expectation is that the *-uros* portion of *saturos* is a suffix or two suffixes together, corresponding to the *-uros* suffix-portion of *marturos*.

If *saturos* derives from PIE $*seh_2$, “to satiate, satisfy”, then very likely so does *Satrai*, the name of an independent and war-like Thracian mountain tribe of Mount Pangaeus who had an oracle of Dionysus on the mountain. The *Satrai* name could have referred to them being shepherds and goatherds as well as skilled warriors, since Latin *pastor* (“shepherd”) derives from PIE $*peh_2$, “to nourish, to feed”; and the name could at the same time have referred to them being worshippers of the Nourisher, a Dionysus-like god who was also surely identified with the sun, and close to the storm-god as well: this

11 Mayrhofer, Manfred (1996) *Etymologisches Wörterbuch des Altindoarischen* [Etymological Dictionary of Old Indo-Aryan], (in German), volume 2, Heidelberg: Carl Winter Universitätsverlag, page 607 .

could be indicated by an oracle up on a mountain, since such sites at high elevations were often dedicated to the sun-god and/or storm-god.

An ethnonym of another Thracian people around there, Satrokentai, could have meant “Offspring of the Nourisher god” or “People of the Nourisher god”, since it was rather common for “tribes” and larger groups of people to name themselves (or to be named by others) after their main deity in their culture. Here, kentai would derive from PIE *ken- “to arise, begin; new, fresh”: from this root by consensus derives Proto-Celtic *kenetlom, “race, people”; and a number of words meaning “child; cub, puppy” etc. In the Thracian language, most authorities believe that the kenthos element occurring in very many Thracian names meant “offspring of” (Kenthos also occurs as a name on its own in Western Thrace sometimes), and in Latin inscriptions of Thrace the element was usually rendered “centus”, without indicating the “th” sound as in the renderings written in the Greek alphabet. It is regular for a nonpalatalized/unpalatalized Proto-Indo-European initial k- sound to remain an initial k- sound in Thracian.

I don’t think that Κένταυρος is cognate to Sanskrit gandharva as was posited in the 19th century: and most linguists in that field will tell you that they don’t match phonetically; nor do I think that Κένταυρος meant “Bull-Goader” as was claimed by someone many centuries ago: I don’t think that’s likely despite the Taurus constellation being identified with winter sometimes, and with the storms of winter; nor am I convinced by Paul Kretschmer’s theory that Κένταυρος meant “Water-Goader”, despite Sagittarius being a constellation of a time of year that is usually rainy in much of Europe: but in Ancient Greek culture, the Centaurus constellation towards the south was the constellation identified with Κένταυρος, not Sagittarius. Κένταυρος in the constellation was thought of as holding a spear with which he is impaling some creature---in a book from 1690 AD/CE, a wolf is being impaled; maybe in some ancient Aegean versions it was a wild boar: the Thracian Horseman deity is sometimes shown impaling a boar.

I’m thinking maybe αυρος (in the form *avros when it entered Greek and became αυρος ?) was one of the Thracian or Pelasgian words for “boar”, which would be cognate to Latin aper, “wild boar” and Proto-Germanic *eburaz, “boar” and Proto-Slavic *veprь “boar, wild boar” et al.; the PIE root is reconstructed by some as *h₁ep-r- .

I have another theory that Κένταυρος may have meant “Born of the wind” referring to an ancient belief in that part of the world---attested in a verse in Vergil’s Georgics (III.274)---that mares were sometimes impregnated by usually invisible spirits known as “winds”; in one well-known Ancient Greek myth Κένταυρος’s mother was a cloud; Ancient Greek αὔρα / αὔρη meant “breeze, wind” and Kent- could be from PIE *ken- “to arise, begin; new, fresh”; and there was a Nereid and an Oceanid named Πληξάουρη (Plêxaurê) whose name very likely meant “whipping wind(s)”¹², referring to a coastal nymph associated with sea-storms probably; Paul Kretschmer posited that Πληξάουρη meant “Water-stinger”, since Πληξ- meant “to strike, to smite, to stamp, to sting”; horses in Ancient Greek myth and culture were closely associated with water and winds: horses were sacred to Poseidon, god of the sea and of fresh-water springs; in the Iliad (XVI.150) we find that the horses of Achilles are born of a Harpy (a creature of the air, that rides the winds) and of Zephyros.

12 Kerényi, Carl (1951). *The Gods of the Greeks*.

A.G., February 9th, 2024